

Dichloroacetic Acid Solvent System. III Solubility of Substances and the Nature of Their Solutions in Dichloroacetic Acid

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Manuscript received 7 August 1978, revised 17 July 1980, accepted 5 November 1980

Solubilities of a large number of solutes in dichloroacetic acid have been determined at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Ionic compounds are sparingly soluble. Iodides and thiocyanates are more soluble than the chlorides and bromides. Tetraalkylammonium halides are very soluble. A number of adducts of Lewis acids and bases with dichloroacetic acid have been isolated. From the conductance, cryoscopic and ir spectral studies, these adducts have been found to be ionic in nature. From the equivalent conductance studies in acetic acid, the adducts $\text{BBr}_3 \cdot \text{CHCl}_2 \cdot \text{COOH}$ and $\text{SbCl}_5 \cdot \text{CHCl}_2 \cdot \text{COOH}$ have been found to be strong Bronsted acids. Conductometric and visual titrations between solvo acids and bases have been carried out in dichloroacetic acid to prove its autoionisation.

ACETIC¹⁻⁵ and monochloroacetic acids⁶⁻¹⁰ have been extensively investigated as medium for the estimation of weakly basic alkaloids, purines, metals etc. From the conductance and heats of solutions of protonic acids in various solvents, it has been shown by Paul and his coworkers¹¹⁻¹³ that dichloroacetic acid is stronger than both acetic and monochloroacetic acids and its strength is comparable to that of methanesulphonic acid. Because of its acidic nature, no compound of Lewis acids with dichloroacetic acid is known in literature while some addition compounds of aromatic amines with it are known^{14,15}. In its adduct with heterocyclic N-oxides, the hydrogen bonded structure of the parent acid is retained^{14,15}. In earlier communications¹⁶⁻¹⁹, we have reported the study of dichloroacetic acid as a non-aqueous solvent. Presently we report the solubility of a number of compounds in it. Behaviour of a number of Lewis acids and bases is being reported.

Experimental

Dichloroacetic acid was purified as reported earlier¹⁶. Most of the solutes used for solubility determination were commercially available A.R. grade samples and were used without further purification. They were, however, kept over P_2O_5 in vacuum desiccator for 48 hrs before use. Lewis acids used were either commercially available or were prepared in the laboratory and were purified by standard methods. Organic tertiary bases were purified by distilling over potassium hydroxide beads before use. Dichloroacetates of alkali metals were prepared and purified by standard methods.

To determine solubility of various solutes, dichloroacetic acid was added to a well dried ampule containing sufficient quantity of the solute.

The ampule was immediately sealed and shaken in a thermostat maintained at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ for 24 hrs. The ampule was then broken. The contents were filtered quickly through a sintered glass funnel in a dry atmosphere. The residue were repeatedly washed with hot benzene to ensure complete removal of dichloroacetic acid. Solubility of the solutes in 100g of dichloroacetic acid was determined by estimating the metal and/or halogen from a known weight of the solution. In most cases, the residues in the sintered glass funnel were the original compounds but in the case of AlCl_3 , AlBr_3 , SnBr_4 , ZrCl_4 , ThCl_4 , BiCl_3 , ZnCl_2 , MgCl_2 , solvates of these compounds were isolated which is due to the stronger acceptor character of these solutes.

Adducts of the bases with dichloroacetic acid were prepared as reported in the case of monochloroacetic acid⁶. In the case of Lewis acids adducts, both the components were mixed in equimolar amounts in liquid sulphur dioxide and the solutions were slowly brought to room temperature. The solvent slowly evaporated leaving behind the solid adducts. All these compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis and are reported in Table 3.

Conductance and potentiometric set up and the techniques of potentiometric and conductometric titrations were the same as reported in fused monochloroacetic acid⁶⁻⁸. Molecular weights were determined in nitrobenzene by Beckmann method. Ir spectra were recorded as nujol mulls and with sodium chloride optics on a double grating Perking-Elmer No. 337 and 621 spectrophotometer; wherever possible transfers were carried out in a dry box.

Results and Discussion

Compared to acetic acid, dichloroacetic acid has a fairly high dipole moment and dielectric constant which would be helpful for the dissolution of ionic compounds. As a first step towards the study of this solvent, the solubility of a number of substances in dichloroacetic acid has been determined at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The results are reported in Table 1. It is evident from the table that strong

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITIES OF VARIOUS SOLUTES IN DICHLOROACETIC ACID AT $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Solute	Amount dissolved in gm/100 ml	Colour of the solution
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NBr}$	9.36	Golden yellow
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{CCl}$	6.34	Brown
SnCl_4	Miscible	Colourless
TiCl_4	"	Light yellow
Pyridine	"	Light pink
HgI_2	Insoluble	—
HgBr_2	"	—
HgCl_2	"	—
BaCl_2	"	—
CdI_2	"	—
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$	15.9	Dark brown
NH_4HF	2.86	Milky
Piperidine	Miscible	Light pink
α -picoline	"	Colourless
Aniline	"	Light brown
$(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{NH}$	"	"
Benzylamine	"	Colourless
SbCl_5	"	Light pink
Bromine	"	Reddish brown
Ammonium Molybdate	Insoluble	—
NH_4Cl	"	—
CoCl_2	"	—
NiCl_2	"	Colourless
PCl_5	Miscible	"
SOCl_2	"	"
KCl	Insoluble	—
Urea	"	—
AlCl_3	0.51	Colourless
Phenylthiourea	26.77	Golden yellow
N-Bromosuccinimide	28.30	Reddish brown
Thiourea	4.5	Colourless
Acetamide	37.4	Pale
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NCl}$	7.42	Colourless
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{NCl}$	8.14	"
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{NI}$	18.32	Light yellow
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{NBr}$	11.76	"
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{NCl}$	10.53	Colourless
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{NBr}$	14.18	Light yellow
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{NI}$	24.56	"
FeCl_3	5.44	Yellow
PCl_3	8.38	"
AsCl_3	Miscible	"
SnBr_4	7.8	"
SiCl_4	Miscible	"
BiCl_3	0.64	"
SbCl_3	2.86	"
ZrCl_4	Insoluble	"
ThCl_4	"	"

donor and acceptor molecules are soluble or miscible with it. Strongly electrovalent compounds are sparingly soluble in it; iodides and thiocyanates are more soluble than the bromides and chlorides. Oxides of iron, chromium, aluminium, cobalt,

nickel, zinc and magnesium are insoluble. Tetramethyl-tetraethyl- and tetrabutyl-ammonium chlorides, bromides and iodides are highly soluble. Tetrabutylammonium salts are more soluble than tetramethylammonium salts. For a particular cation, the iodides are more soluble than bromides and chlorides. But when these salts are added in excess, compounds of composition $\text{R}_4\text{N} \cdot \text{CHCl}_2 \cdot \text{COO}$ separate out from the solution. Alkali metal dichloroacetates are less soluble than tetraalkylammonium dichloroacetates. It is interesting to note that barium chloride, strontium halides, calcium chloride and tetrachlorides of selenium and tellurium do not form any solvate with this solvent showing its poor donor character. Copper chloride, nickel chloride and cobalt chloride are insoluble in it. However, thiocyanates of nickel and cobalt are fairly soluble in this medium. Chlorides of zinc and cadmium form solvates of composition $\text{MCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CHCl}_2 \cdot \text{COOH}$ while halides of mercury are insoluble in it. Trichlorides of phosphorus, arsenic and antimony do not form any solvate with dichloroacetic acid but bismuth trichloride forms a solvate of composition $\text{BiCl}_3 \cdot \text{CHCl}_2 \cdot \text{COOH}$. Qualitative tests have shown that the solubility of the most of the solutes increases with rise in temperature. Compared to acetic acid, ionic compounds are more soluble in dichloroacetic acid. Only stronger Lewis acids form solid adducts with dichloroacetic acid while Lewis bases readily form adducts with it.

By analogy with other strong protonic acids²⁰⁻²², a possible mode of self ionisation of dichloroacetic acid may be proposed as:

Conductances of the solutions of Lewis acids and bases, quaternary ammonium salts and alkali metal dichloroacetates have been determined at $25.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$ at different concentrations. The results are given in Table 2. It is quite surprising that the

TABLE 2—MOLAR CONDUCTANCE OF THE SOLUTIONS OF VARIOUS SOLUTES IN DICHLOROACETIC ACID AT $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

Solute	Molarity of Solution	Molar conductance $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
Diethylamine	$.545 \times 10^{-4}$	14.626
Pyridine	$.34 \times 10^{-4}$	13.286
α -Picoline	$.7 \times 10^{-4}$	13.962
Piperidine	$.1122 \times 10^{-3}$	10.64
Benzylamine	$.32 \times 10^{-3}$	2.97
Quinoline	$.81 \times 10^{-4}$	12.0
AlBr_3	$.926 \times 10^{-3}$	1.1
SnCl_4	$.142 \times 10^{-2}$	0.74
ZrCl_4	$.85 \times 10^{-3}$	1.10
TiCl_4	$.5 \times 10^{-4}$	17.6000
SbCl_5	$.171 \times 10^{-2}$	1.048
$(\text{CH}_3)_4\text{NI}$	$.44 \times 10^{-3}$	3.6209
$(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{NI}$	$.13 \times 10^{-3}$	9.6069
KI	$.16 \times 10^{-3}$	6.6175
$(\text{ClH}_2)_4\text{NBr}$	$.14 \times 10^{-3}$	9.9207

molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions of the quaternary ammonium halides and tertiary nitrogen compounds are very high compared to those of the dichloroacetates of alkali metals. It is very difficult to explain this unusual behaviour. Nevertheless the molar conductance values are quite high and are comparable to fairly ionised solutions in other polar solvents. Increase in the conductance of dichloroacetic acid on the addition of tertiary bases is due to the formation of strongly polar solvates which ionise in solutions to furnish ions. These may yield $\text{CHCl}_2\text{COO}^-$ and the appropriate ammonium ion in the solution. Similarly, in the case of the Lewis acid adducts where both the reactants are practically non-conducting, the high conductance of their solutions may be due to the ionisation of the adducts such as :

Further information about the nature of the ions present in the solutions and in the solid state has been obtained by isolating the adducts. In Table 3 is given a list of the adducts which have been isolated. Only very strong acceptor molecules form adducts with dichloroacetic acid suggesting its weak donor character. Except for the tetrahalides of the group IV elements wherein the compounds isolated are of 1 : 2 stoichiometric composition, the other metal halides form compounds of 1 : 1 composition indicating that dichloroacetic acid acts as a monodentate ligand. All these adducts are extremely hygroscopic and have low melting points. From the molar conductance values of their millimolar solutions in various aprotic solvents, it is evident that they are ionised in solution which is also supported by the molecular weight determinations.

Dichloroacetic acid has a sharp intense absorption band at 1742 cm^{-1} assigned to the carbonyl stretching mode. It also has a broad absorption band at 3430 cm^{-1} due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding. The spectra of pure carboxylic acids are known to have peaks near 1400 and 1300 cm^{-1} which arise from O—C stretching vibrations²³ but coupled with OH vibrations in a plane formation vibration. It is thus not possible to study the O—C stretching vibrations of these adducts as has been done in the case of the adducts of esters²⁴. Attention has therefore been focussed only on the changes in the absorption frequencies due to the carbonyl frequencies.

It is interesting to note that on adduct formation with Lewis acids, the absorption bands due to the OH group of dichloroacetic acid becomes very sharp except in the case of weak acceptors such as ZnCl_2 , MgCl_2 etc. It seems that in the case of adducts of the stronger Lewis acids, the intermolecular hydrogen bonded structure is ruptured. On adduct formation, the withdrawal of electrons from the carbonyl oxygen weakens the hydrogen bond and strengthens the adjacent O—H bond.

A decrease of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching mode from 1742 cm^{-1} in pure dichloroacetic acid to 1692 , 1712 , 1718 , 1726 and 1730 cm^{-1} on adduct formation with SbCl_5 , BBr_3 , TiCl_4 and SnCl_4 respectively suggests the carbonyl oxygen to be the donor site and the following order of the acceptor strength :

From the molar conductance values and its spectrum in the solid state, possible behaviour of the solutions of boron tribromide in dichloroacetic acid may be postulated as :

A new doublet at 518 cm^{-1} is also observed. The band at 538 cm^{-1} is analogous to the degenerate $\nu_4(\text{B}-\text{Cl})$ bending mode in BCl_4^- . The doublet can be attributed to the change in the local symmetry from T_d to C_{3v} for the boron²⁵. In both the compounds of boron, a strong new absorption band is observed around 1100 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to a B—X stretching mode analogous to ν_4 but this is coupled with the B—O stretching mode which also occurs in the same region²⁶. In the case of antimony pentachloride adduct, a new absorption band appears at 412 cm^{-1} which has been assigned to antimony-oxygen stretching mode²⁷. The absorption bands at 340 and 650 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the antimony-chlorine stretching mode in an octahedral environment of the metal²⁸. The antimony has achieved an octahedral environment by combining with the carbonyl oxygen of the dichloroacetic acid. The possible ions may be formulated as :

Similarly in the case of titanium tetrachloride, apart from the lowering of the carbonyl stretching mode, there is appearance of a sharp intense band at 430 cm^{-1} due to titanium-oxygen stretching mode. The bands at 628 and 320 cm^{-1} assigned to metal chlorine²⁹ stretching mode in octahedral

TABLE 3—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE ADDUCTS OF LEWIS ACIDS AND BASES WITH DICHLOROACETIC ACID

Compound	Colour	Elemental Analysis				Molecular weight		Molar conductance in methyl cyanide $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$
		%Age		Reqd.		Calculated	Found	
		Cl	Metal/Nitrogen	Cl	Metal/Nitrogen			
$\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}\cdot\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$	White	34.20	6.48	34.13	6.88	208	98	72.8
$\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}\cdot\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{N}$	White	33.10	6.34	33.17	6.54	214	106	55.3
$\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}\cdot\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$	White	28.97	5.02	29.83	5.92	236	108	58.0
$\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}\cdot\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$	Yellow	31.98	6.30	32.43	6.30	222	110	39.9
$\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{CH}_2\text{N}$	Light Brown	31.98	6.30	32.43	6.30	222	105	37.8*
$\text{TiCl}_4\cdot 2\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}$	White	62.95	10.55	63.38	10.71	446	288	42.5*
$\text{SbCl}_5\cdot\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}$	Light Yellow	52.27	27.83	57.99	28.47	428	246	28.7
$\text{SnCl}_4\cdot 2\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}$	Grey	40.62	22.12	41.04	22.93	519	296	22.5
$\text{BBr}_3\cdot\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}$	White	80.69**	—	81.98**	—	380	212	31.9*

** Total amount of halogen.
* in nitrobenzene.

environment are also observed. The possible ions may be formulated as :

Since the adducts of Lewis acids with dichloroacetic acid are proton donors, it is of interest to compare their acid strength with other mineral acids. Acetic acid has been used as a differentiating solvent^{30,31}. The adducts $\text{BBr}_3\cdot\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}$ and $\text{SbCl}_5\cdot\text{CHCl}_2\text{COOH}$ are fairly soluble and ionised in acetic acid. A plot of equivalent conductance versus concentration has been drawn for these adducts and is given in Fig. 1. The values of the equivalent conductance at infinite dilution have

Fig. 1. Equivalent conductance curves of strong acids in acetic acid.

been found to be fairly high. For a comparison, the reported curves for other mineral acids in acetic acid are also included. From the figure, it is evident that these adducts are fairly strong Bronsted acids and their order of increasing acid strength is as :

It is evident from Table 3 that a large number of organic nitrogen bases form solid adducts with dichloroacetic acid. The nature of the solution in dichloroacetic acid has been elucidated by ir spectral studies of their solid adducts. For brevity only representative spectra of the complexes are discussed. It is observed that in these complexes, the spectral bands of the pure compounds undergo the same changes and in the same order as occur in the formation of pyridinium chloride³², complexes of acetyl chloride³³ and tertiary bases and also in the case of compounds of selenium tetrachloride and pyridine³⁴.

Pyridine, quinoline, α -picoline, piperidine etc act as donors towards Lewis acids forming complexes where the nitrogen atom of the tertiary base donates electrons to the vacant orbital of the central metal atom. Principal bands of the ir spectra of these compounds are given in Table 4. The assignments of various bands of pyridine, quinoline, α -picoline, morpholine and piperidine are based on Wimshrest and Bernstein³⁵, Green and Wade³⁶ and Sharp and his coworkers³⁷. The strong bands at 1583, 1572, 1483 and 1440 cm^{-1} in pyridine are due to the C=C and C=N symmetric and anti-symmetric stretching vibrations. It is evident that the donation by the nitrogen of pyridine will increase the double bond character of the C=C and C=N bonds because of the reduction of electron density on the nitrogen. The new bands observed in the complex at 1622, 1608, 1503 and 1480 cm^{-1} are nearly at the same position as those for the

TABLE 4—PRINCIPAL IR BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF THE COMPLEXES OF DICHLOROACETIC ACID WITH ORGANIC BASES

Pyridine	Quinoline	α -Picoline	Piperidine
2940s	2946s	2942s	2941s
2720b	2706b	2710b	2722b
1622s	1686s	1646s	1648s
1608s	1622s	1626s	1626s
1509s	1604s	1616m	1610m
1480	1560m	1600s	1595m
1432s	1426s	1440s	1436s
1385s	1388	1392	1384
1322s	1318s	1320s	1306s
1250s	1258	1262	1266
1204s	1225s	1232s	1212s
1165	1168	1176	1174
1052s	1042s	1040s	1038s
1000s	1004s	1006s	1006s
890s	892s	890s	892s
751vs	744vs	744vs	740vs
680vs	682vs	677vs	674vs

pyridinium ion. The two strong bands in the adduct at 1385 and 1322 cm⁻¹ are at the same position as those in the pyridinium ion. Pyridine has a very weak absorption at 1377 cm⁻¹ which is intensified and shifts a little in the pyridinium ion complex. A new band at 1432 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to the N—N stretching frequency.

The three bands appearing in the complex at 1250, 1204 and 1165 cm⁻¹ are due to the C—H inplane deformation of pyridine which are observed at 1220, 1152 and 1072 cm⁻¹ in the free base. The shift to the higher frequency is due to the withdrawal of electron density from the C—H bond. The above mentioned bands are at the same position as those for the pyridinium ion in pyridinium chloride. The next three bands at 1052, 1028 and 1000 cm⁻¹ which are observed in the ir spectrum of the present complex are also at similar position in the pyridinium chloride. These bands arise from the deformation of the pyridine ring. They appear at 1034 and 993 cm⁻¹ on complex formation. A strong band at 890 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the complex is present in pyridine at 887 cm⁻¹ as a weak band. Two bands at 751 and 680 cm⁻¹ in the complex are in the same position as in PyH⁺.Cl⁻ (753 and 680 cm⁻¹) while pyridine absorbs at 784 and 705 cm⁻¹. Thus all the changes in the spectrum of the pure pyridine corresponds to the formation of a pyridinium ion.

The spectral changes in the complexes of the other tertiary organic bases follow a similar pattern as protonated cations. These complexes are different from those of Lewis acids and the possible ions may be formulated as :

It is evident from the above studies that both Lewis acids and bases form conducting solutions

when dissolved in dichloroacetic acid. It may be possible to carry out acid-base titration between Lewis acids and bases in dichloroacetic acid. These titrations have been followed conductometrically, potentiometrically and with the help of visual indicators. Crystal violet, malachite green and benzenthron have been used as visual indicators. The colours of these indicators in acidic and basic media in dichloroacetic acid are the same as in the aqueous medium. The changes in the colours near the end points are very sharp. The results are reproducible and the indicators can act reversibly. In Figs. 2 and 3 are given the conductometric and potentiometric titrations curves for boron tribromide against pyridine and tetrabutylammonium dichloroacetic acid along with those of other bases. Acid-base neutralisation reaction may be represented as :

Similarly in the case of antimony pentachloride, the possible reaction may be represented as :

The decrease in the conductance of the solution on the addition of the acidic solution is due to the removal of CHCl₂COO⁻ ions. At the molar ratio acid/base of 1 : 1 when there is complete removal of

 Fig. 2. Conductometric titration between BBr₃.CHCl₂COOH and bases at 25° ± 0.1.

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titrations between BBr_3 and bases in $CHCl_2COOH$.

$CHCl_2COO^-$ ions, further addition of $CHCl_2COOH^+$ ions causes an increase in the conductance of the solutions. The presence of only one break in the conductance composition curves shows that both $SbCl_5 \cdot CHCl_2COOH$ and $BBr_3 \cdot CHCl_2COOH$ behave as monobasic acids. As the breaks in the diagram are not very sharp, it shows that the acid formed are quite weak. In the case of the adducts of tetrachlorides of tin and titanium, there are two breaks in the conductance composition curves corresponding to the molar ratio acid/base of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 confirming the dibasic character of these Lewis acids. All these investigations support the ionic nature of the medium and the mode of autoionisation of the solvent may be proposed as :

References

1. C. W. PEPPER and E. G. WOLLISH, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 300.
2. I. M. KOLTHOFF and A. WILLMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1007.
3. G. F. NADREAU and L. E. BRANCHEN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1363.
4. R. C. PAUL, S. K. VASISTH, K. C. MALHOTRA and S. S. PAHIL, *Analyt. Chem.*, 1962, 34, 820.
5. R. C. PAUL, K. R. KAPOOR and S. S. PAHIL, *Research Bulletin, Panjab University (N.S.)*, 1963, 14, 29.

6. K. C. MALHOTRA and R. G. SUD, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 36, 3767.
7. K. C. MALHOTRA and R. G. SUD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 277.
8. K. C. MALHOTRA and R. G. SUD, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 380.
9. K. C. MALHOTRA and R. G. SUD, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1976, 38, 384.
10. K. C. MALHOTRA and R. G. SUD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 1018.
11. R. C. PAUL, K. K. PAUL and K. C. MALHOTRA, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1963, 70, 321.
12. R. C. PAUL, J. SINGH, S. C. AHLUWALIA and S. S. PAHIL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 134.
13. R. C. PAUL, S. C. AHLUWALIA, S. K. REHANI and S. S. PAHIL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 207.
14. MIROSLAW SZAFRAN and DEGA SZAFRAN, *Roocz. Chem.*, 1970, 44, 793; *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 74, 3240s.
15. DEGA SZAFRAN, ZOFIA NASKRET-BARCISZEWSKA, Z. MIROSLAW and SZAFRAN MIROSLAW, *Roocz. Chem.*, 1973, 47, 749; *Chem. Abs.*, 1973, 79, 91391y.
16. K. C. MALHOTRA, O. P. SHARMA and S. C. CHAUDHRY, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1973, 999.
17. K. C. MALHOTRA and R. G. SUD, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1976, 29, 1931.
18. K. C. MALHOTRA, GRETA MEHROTRA, V. P. MAHAJAN and S. C. CHAUDHRY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, 31, 967.
19. K. C. MALHOTRA, V. P. MAHAJAN and GRETA MEHROTRA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 17A, 148.
20. R. C. PAUL, S. K. VASHISTH, K. C. MALHOTRA and S. S. PAHIL, *J. Scient. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 218, 552.
21. J. BARR, R. J. GILLESPIE and R. C. THOMPSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1149.
22. S. WASIF, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 1324.
23. I. LINDQVIST and M. SACKERSON, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, 17, 29.
24. M. F. LAPPART, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 542.
25. J. G. JONES, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, 5, 1229.
26. B. P. SUSZ and P. CHALADON, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1958, 41, 699.
27. K. C. MALHOTRA and S. M. SEHGAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, 12, 982.
28. I. R. BEATTIS and G. R. MEQUILLAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1519.
29. D. COOK, S. J. KUHN and G. A. OLAH, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1969, 33, 1669.
30. H. J. EMELRUS, R. N. HAZELDINE and R. C. PAUL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 563.
31. I. M. KOLTHOFF and WILLMAN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1007.
32. N. N. GREEN and K. WADE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1667.
33. R. C. PAUL and S. L. CHADHA, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1966, 22, 615.
34. A. W. CORDES and T. V. HUGHES, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1640.
35. J. K. WIMSHURST and H. J. BERNSTEIN, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1957, 35, 1185.
36. N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTTALL, D. E. SOAIFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, 18, 79.